

FACTORS AFFECTING THE USE OF LABOR RESOURCES IN ANDIZHAN DISTRICT

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Annotation: As in the whole country, the problems of employment and unemployment are urgent not only in Andijan region but also in Andijan district. Rational use of labor resources will allow our country to overcome the current social, economic, demographic, employment, unemployment, migration and other problems.

Keywords: population, employment problems, unemployment, demography, labor resources.

It is expedient to use the experience of other countries, especially Western Europe and especially East Asia, in the development of the national economy, which is typical of the transition to market relations, and thereby increase the welfare of the population.

Based on the strategy and tactics developed in the process of economic development of the republic, structural changes are being carried out. In particular, a number of achievements have been made in the development of industry, raising the agro-industrial complex to a new level, improving the transport system depending on its geographical location. At the same time, efforts are being made to use the existing mineral and agricultural raw materials and labor resources in the regions, as well as the ancient national handicrafts and labor skills of the people.

Our country has a strong labor potential, which raises the problem of effective use of this powerful labor potential in some regions of the country. The main issue for this is the structural redistribution of the employed population and the involvement of able-bodied youth in new advanced sectors and industries of the economy.

It is known that a large part of the population is engaged in agriculture. That is why it is precisely the reorientation of agricultural labor resources to other sectors of the economy, primarily industry and services, that opens up vast opportunities for structural changes in the economy and its rapid development.

As a result of structural changes in the economy, the extensive and effective use of the potential of the regions creates new forms of regional specialization. In particular, the industry of Navoi, Tashkent and Kashkadarya regions is developing due to fuel and mineral resources, and the Khorezm and Fergana Valley regions

are developing due to rich labor resources. The establishment of new economic centers will further increase their economic potential in the country.

However, it cannot be said that the internal potential of all regions, in particular, labor resources, is being widely used. Especially in the densely populated Andijan region, this issue has become a topical issue and is waiting for its solution. After all, due to high natural growth, many young people are joining the labor force. This further complicates the problem of their employment.

Today, Andijan region is one of the most difficult regions of Uzbekistan in terms of its demographic situation. As a result, many economic and social problems have arisen in the region. A lot of work is being done to address these issues. In particular, new jobs are being created through the development of industry, and the demand for labor resources is being met, albeit partially. At the same time, the socio-economic situation in some districts is becoming more complicated as a result of insufficient attention to this topical issue. Socio-economic problems of Andijan region are largely explained by high natural population growth, composition, territorial location, and the problem of rational and efficient use of labor resources is one of the most important issues today and is waiting for a positive solution.

In Andijan region, there are issues of formation of labor resources at the level of individual cities and districts, their effective use, and the importance of in-depth and comprehensive study of these issues determines the relevance of the chosen topic.

At the current stage of transition to market relations, among the major tasks are the assessment of the current demographic situation in the country, the need for social protection of the majority of the population and most of them live in rural areas, employment and labor development.

The demographic situation also has a significant impact on Uzbekistan's choice of its path of socio-economic development. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, which has a unique population structure, relatively high birth rate and natural population growth, including Andijan district, the issue of employment has always been and remains one of the most pressing and complex issues. Rapid population growth is further expanding the ranks of the labor force. Human resource management is a complex issue that combines the processes of demographic development, employment, from vocational training to the efficient use of labor.

The study of the processes taking place in the Republic of Uzbekistan, including Andijan district, on the modernization of the economy and employment in the conditions of innovative development has led to the following conclusions:

1. In recent years, significant positive changes have taken place in the field of employment in the context of modernization of the economy and innovative development:

The current structural changes in the country to ensure employment include:

- Improving the employment structure of the population and training the unemployed in new, competitive occupations in the labor market.
- Increased focus on modernization, technical and technological re-equipment of production, especially restructuring and diversification. This includes the creation of new jobs, as well as the production of new products and services for domestic and foreign consumption.
- Improving the activities of employment centers, first of all, optimizing the structure of these centers, setting priorities in the context of the global crisis, the rational allocation of funds for employment based on the objectives of socio-economic development requires.

2. The measures taken to create jobs have played an important socio-economic role in employment and social protection:

- compactness of the organization of the economy and their rapid adaptation to the market environment;
- Belonging of household members to a particular family;
- Possibility to organize production at the expense of the family;
- Convenience in the organization of labor and management of the farm.

3. Substantiating the demographic aspects of the use of labor in the context of rapid growth of labor resources in Andijan district will allow to effectively organize this process:

- While the declining trend in the birth rate has led to a decrease in the proportion of children in the population, the fact that generations born in the past with high birth rates are now entering the working age has led to a higher share of labor resources. As a result, the burden on children of labor resources is declining from year to year.

4. The main directions and prospects of labor market regulation have been identified and scientific proposals and recommendations for its improvement have been developed.

The main goal of the concept of development of the labor market of the republic, which is well supplied with labor resources, is to solve the problems of reducing employment of the working age population, reducing labor productivity, inflation. The gradual emergence of various forms of ownership, the very slow

implementation of structural changes in the economy, the reduction of real incomes, the development of complex measures to increase labor demand and reduce its supply. They will be developed based on the strategic goals of deep, structural and liberalization reform of the national economy of Uzbekistan in the transition period.

The following conclusions can be drawn from the research:

1. In solving the problems of Andijan district, the existing land area is very small, which makes it difficult to build new production facilities.
2. The desire of a significant part of the population and labor resources to be located in the regional center, ie in Andijan district, which creates problems with labor resources.
3. Presence of ancient national-ethnic features of the population of Andijan district, the level of urbanization, the presence of widespread national customs, traditions, labor skills and other ethnopsychological features in the valley. The above features should be taken into account when solving employment problems.
4. It is necessary to solve the problem of employment in Andijan district in connection with the prospects for the near future development of other cities and towns and villages of the region. In addition to "pure" economic factors, it is necessary to take into account the geographical, demographic, environmental conditions.
5. Special attention should be paid to the study and in-depth analysis of the formation and development of the labor market and their forecasting.
6. The number of new jobs created is much lower than the number of growing labor resources. This shows that the problem of efficient use of labor resources, which is still very relevant today, will remain in the future.

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